

The Relevance of Swami Vivekananda's Uses of English Language in Today's Teaching-Learning Situation—A Socio-Linguistic Enquiry

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ABSTRACT : The present article focuses on the similarity between the thoughts of Swami Vivekananda on language and the views of FCA. English language as used by Sw. Vivekananda in his numerous writings and speeches may be a model for the Indian people (especially the learners and teachers) to meet the present demands.

Keywords : English Language Teaching, FCA, teaching-learning situation.

Introduction

India, as we know, is a multi-cultural and multi-lingual society with a perennial unity. English is in India today a symbol of people's aspirations for quality in education and a fuller participation in national and international life. Its colonial origins now forgotten or irrelevant, its initial role in independent India, tailored to higher education (as a "*library language*", a "*window on the world*"), now felt to be insufficiently

inclusive socially and linguistically, the current status of English stems from its overwhelming presence on the world stage and the reflection of this in the national arena. The visible impact of this presence of English is that it is today being demanded by everyone at the very initial stage of schooling. The opening up of the Indian economy in the 1990s has coincided with an explosion in the demand for English in our schools because English is perceived to open

up opportunities. The impact of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization(LPG), the market-driven economy, the upsurge of social needs have made the English language an economic necessity and this “**English advantage**” has become India’s selling point in the national as well as international arena. It is widely used in the domain of education, administration, trade and commerce, communication etc. However when it comes to learning of English, unlike L_1 and the national language, people do not have an acquisition rich environment. Only a few people in India are born and brought up in English speaking families. Therefore, we do not have many people around us speaking in English. Therefore learning English is not the same as learning L_1 . Learners of English in India seldom get opportunity for getting exposure to the language. Perhaps classroom is the only place wherein they get opportunity for exposure. In case the exposure they get there happens to be poor, their chance for picking up the language can also be dismal. Hence there was a widespread reaction against methods of teaching English that stressed the teaching of grammatical forms and paid little attention to the way language is used in everyday communication. A concern then developed to make English communicative by focusing on learner’s knowledge of the functions of language and their ability to select appropriate kinds of language for use in specific situations. Against this background FCA emerged and gained a world-wide acceptance from 1984 till date. In the teaching-learning process of second (or foreign) language this method is very popular and has proved its efficacy. Students may be able to deal with four competencies-communicative, grammatical, strategic and psycho-linguistic. If we take into account the

salient features of FCA under our review, then the following may be noted—

- i. The goal of LT is to develop communicative competence- learners learn to communicate by communicating- by practice- by drilling.
- ii. In this approach all communications will take place in the target language, mother tongue is applicable only when it is extremely needed.
- iii. Functions of the language are emphasized rather than the rules and regulations.

English in the Classrooms of India

The present picture related to classroom teaching is simply discouraging as teaching, now-a-days, has become mostly information –laden, as a result, learners are suffering from a grotesque disease, namely, paper thirst or readymade answer thirst instead of wonder-thirst. In this running track, they are gradually retreating from their ability to think, to imagine and to speak. Most of us would agree that a second or foreign language is learnt not so much by direct instruction in its rules as by using it in meaningful contexts, especially when the students’ experience, interests and knowledge of the world are involved. Language is not only a tacit and formal system of sounds, words and syntactical structures, language also sensitizes the vibrant domain of human interaction. Language is the abode of being; it is the fundamental signs of our humanity. Language is the palette from which people color their lives. Language is a social phenomenon and language learning is therefore a social activity. A child learns a language with reference to various socio-cultural contexts. Language learning does

not entail only knowing the language in L_1 or L_2 , but also knowing how to use language in situations and contexts. While learning second/foreign language, every native speaker assimilates his individual and social experiences which are simply the reflection of his own culture. A child learning a language is learning about the world, about how it works. Locating our attention to the situation of English (L_2 or foreign language whatever we may call it) in India at present we may find that we had neither any feeling nor do have any cultural empathy with English; we just need English for our material prosperity and nothing else. English Language Teaching (ELT) in India has been from the disease of '*shadow mind*' – a virtual, inauthentic Indian mind functioning under the colonial hangover. This is due to the incongruous and incomplete mind-set of the Indians about ELT in which culture-specific pedagogy remains a mirage all along. But there remains another story on the other side of the canvas, i.e., the recently developed attitude to English language in India. This sudden English boom is due to the Globalization, the Liberalization of the economy, the opening of the world-wide market, and the job opportunities across the globe. So, the simultaneous existence of so called artificial light and original darkness, so called success and genuine pathos go hand in hand in English Language Teaching in India. To avoid such sort of circumstances, English Language teachers and learners should try collaboratively to achieve a simplified version of the target language in their own way which is mostly suited to their soil. Teachers can be more deliberate in facilitating learners learn to experience reality in a new way. Coming to this point, we may aptly generalize the fact that FCA can be the most suitable

approach in the teaching-learning situation of English language in India.

There is no need to be frustrating because a man from our country- a religious master, a prophet and a visionary- Swami Vivekananda highlighted the Indian spirit over the seas and he did it in his own way, by delivering the words unhesitatingly by the valor of his tongue or pen. Simplicity was the hallmark of his language (obviously English is spoken of). His language was of the kind in which people normally think and communicate. There are ample evidences of similarities between his practice of English language and the ideals of FCA. Hence, besides being felt proud of, a review of Swami Vivekananda's conception on language and solely for our purpose the uses of English language are mostly relevant in the present teaching-learning scenario of English where communicative competence is the prime concern.

Swami Vivekananda on Language

St. Augustine, as quoted in Eric Auerbach, said, "*Language should follow the voice of conscience; our voice and behavior should supplement to each other.*" As great men think alike, Swami Vivekananda's ideal on language was unique-

The language in which we naturally express ourselves, in which we communicate our anger, grief, or love, etc. –there cannot be a fitter language than that. We must stick to that idea, that manner of expression, that diction and all. No artificial language can ever have that force, and that brevity and expressiveness, or admit of being given any turn you please, as that spoken

language. Language must be made like pure steel- turn and twist it any way you like, it is again the same – it cleaves a rock in twain at one stroke, without its edge being turned. (*The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda*, Vol.VI, 1969, P. 190)

Simplicity was the secret. His ideal language was his master's language, most colloquial and yet most expressive. It must express the thought which was intended to be conveyed. Sister Nivedita was also reminiscent of the fact that Swamiji encouraged her time and again to express herself in her own way. When Nivedita conveyed her realization that she thought it better to speak to a man in his own language Swamiji affirmed her by quoting his Guru,

... Ramakrishna Paramhansa was the only man who taught that! He was the only man who ever had the courage to say that we must speak to all men in their own language! (*Complete Works of Sister Nivedita*, Vol.I, P.118)

In short, Vivekananda pleaded that language should be of the kind in which people normally think and communicate. The ultimatum is the overall simplification of language as to be nurtured by people in their day to day use with less labored diction and simple construction. Hence he wanted to propagate a common language to be treated as the language of the masses.

Swami Vivekananda's concern about English seemed to have emerged from his concern about his native Indian people. He was well aware of the origin of the very language but did not go for mere imitation. Rather, he tried to make an Indianized version of the British language which

would be handier to deal with for his countrymen, the masses. His views on language (viz. English, Sanskrit, Bengali) may be noted in the following way—

- i. Language must be simple
- ii. Any language lives in communication, i.e., language of the mouth is more important than language in the black and white
- iii. Language must be understood by all irrespective of academically viable and academically marginalized
- iv. Language must be accompanied by the spread of education, the panacea of all evils
- v. Language must be indigenous and culture specific
- vi. Language must be originated from the Indian soil.

Swami Vivekananda's Mastery of English Language

Sw. Vivekananda displayed a perfect mastery of English language. To say, it was a happy by-product of his assimilation of Western influences in the exercise of his original creative faculties. He exhibited such a depth of understanding and his mode of presentation in simple understandable language bought him name and fame. His knowledge of English is as though it were his mother tongue. In America, before the meeting of the Parliament of Religions, he had created an impression in the circle he moved about and Marie Louis Burke quoted a letter of Mrs. Wright, wife of Prof. John Henry Wright of Annisquam, dated August 29, 1883 to her mother,

In quoting from the Upanishads his voice was most musical. He would quote a verse in Sanskrit, with intonations, and then translate it into beautiful English, of which he had a wonderful command. And in his mystical religion he seemed perfectly and unquestionably happy... (*Swami Vivekananda in America: New Discoveries*, 1958. P.26)

Apart from the fact that he had a wonderful command of the English language, and his voice was musical and his logic penetrating, his saffron robes created a devastating effect. Among the many tributes paid to Swami Vivekananda on the occasion of inaugural speech in the Parliament, one that deserves quoting and which is relevant to our purpose is that by the famous poetess Harriet Monroe. She records in her autobiography:

But the handsome monk in the orange robe gave us in perfect English a masterpiece... (*Swami Vivekananda in America: New Discoveries*, 1958. P.59)

There is however, one note of caution. Whatever one speaks or writes with a purpose is in a sense propagandist in character. It is very much true that all of Sw. Vivekananda's writings and sayings are goal oriented. So the question of deliberation is no doubt pertinent. For the time being if we regard it as a true fact, then it can be said that without having much mastery over the language one cannot mend the language to serve one's own purpose. Obviously he had a great mission to bring the Vedas into household practices across the globe. Side by side he had to canvas the hidden glory of the Hindu religion, arouse the people of his nation to their consciousness et al. To attain all these he set out with a profound knowledge for a worldwide

campaigning. He achieved acceptance across the globe through the power of his language (English to say) and the process of his rendering. It is more convincing that he did not practice oratory as an art, study elocution and have the slightest desire to build a career for himself. If we follow his discourses with others, we will find that all the answers he made were prompt and there was never any intention to mystify or making difficult. He used to speak excellent English and reply readily to any questions asked in sincerity. Such a readiness does not affirm his deliberation. He spoke and wrote so often and with such intensity of feeling that he could hardly find the time or be in the mood to pause and refine his sentences. The words gushed out as it were and carried with them the native energy and impetuosity of his mind and his feeling for the common people.

The several volumes of his complete works, published by the Advaita Ashrama, comprise courses of lectures on the different Yogas (Raja, Jnana, Bhakti and Karma) and on the Gita, and numerous talks, essays and letters covering sacred as well as secular themes. For our current purpose we will analyze Sw. Vivekananda's letters and speeches written and delivered in English respectively to consider how far his theory on language and practices are in parity.

Uses of English Language by Sw. Vivekananda in his Letters

Sw. Vivekananda was a great letter writer. His epistles are specimens of a giant force latent in sparkling words and act like electric shocks. He knew that no artificial language could ever have that force, that brevity, that expressiveness as the spoken language. His language of writing was not different from the language he spoke.

Here we find a similar conception with William Wordsworth, the renowned poet of English literature, who opined that the language of poetry must be the same as the spoken language. Written without thought of publication, Sw. Vivekananda's uses of English language are more relaxed and informal. Vigor, forcefulness and strength are the most obvious qualities of the language. Most of the letters are purposefully written and they are mainly vehicles for the great mission in his life. They opened up vistas of literary promise, which if persisted, might have given the world a literary giant. Sw. Vivekananda's letters get permanent literary value because of their intrinsic quality and lucidity of thought. Nobility of diction caters inspiration and creates aspiration among the readers. His vast erudition in English in an age of cultural impact from the West raises cyclone in souls with a sense of burning nationalism. The language is replete with a circle of aphorisms and draws references from various resources. The greatness lies in the fact that his language is loaded with insight and practical wisdom to become current proverbs:

Education is the manifestation of the perfection already in man. (*Abridged Edition of The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda*, 1985, P. 506)

In a letter to the Maharaja of Mysore dated 23rd June, 1894 Swamiji wrote that a man should be totally dedicated to the wellbeing of other fellow human beings:

My noble prince, this life is short, the vanities of the world are transient, but they alone live who live for others, the rest are more dead than alive. (*Abridged Edition of The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda*, 1985, P. 510)

Again in a letter to Raja Pyari Mohan Mukherjee dated 18th November, 1894 he discussed about the downfall of India and the reason to be found out by the great monk is the contraction of human nature to be remedied as “*Expansion is life, contraction is death*” (*Abridged Edition of The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda*, 1985, P. 511). Such in numerous letters his language is very much simple and purposeful. To say his language has the force of a hammer which strikes at the point it aims at. It is to be noted that Swamiji's writings towards his Western followers is markedly different from his Indian ones. While in the first case he often used complex as well as compound sentences and ecstatic words, in the latter one he switched to somewhat easy, simple and less labored diction. This elucidates his indigenous and culture specific nature of language.

A General Estimation of Sw. Vivekananda's Speeches and Inspiring Talks

The first positive influence of Sw. Vivekananda's personality is his oratory and his in-depth knowledge of the English language. The way he spoke in English about the Gita and the Upanishads greatly impressed the audience across the globe. He explained the great Gita and made it very easy for the common man (the mass). His exemplary English, his punctuality and his way of touching the hearts of everyone was his specialty. His witty and intelligent examples used to support his views and opinions. Swamiji's enthusiasm, his power of expression and ability to sustain the audience's interest for one hour or more is as good and effective as to the present day. His lectures are in beautifully, flowing, simple English and this makes it easy to understand and assimilate. He wanted the

upliftment and freedom of the Indian people, the material and moral advancement of the same. By the word 'people', he did not mean a political term, but the masses that constitute the major portion of humanity living in India. Swamiji's language was explicit in nature and motivated towards the betterment of Indian people. He had the gift of picking up examples from different sources to illustrate or compare anything. To illustrate the living condition of Indian people of the then time he ones compared them with hewers of wood and drawers of water. This habit is very much akin to the practice of using metaphysical conceits by poets like John Donne, Andrew Marvell et al who belonged to the school of metaphysical poets of English literature. It can unhesitatingly be said that Sw. Vivekananda was a born orator. From the Himalayas to the Kanyakumarika he preached to his fellow people the lessons of mildness, gentleness, sympathy and brotherhood, whether learned or unlearned, without any respect of race, caste or creed. Apart from the fact that he had a wonderful command over the English language the verbal felicity and the rhythmic dexterity gave a punch to his talk and added a sincerity which could appeal straight to the hearts of million devotees. He spoke with knowledge and conviction and a sense of urgency, and he was a very effective speaker, bold, audacious, fluent, and essentially educative.

In the Art Institute Building, on Monday, 11th September, 1893 at the far end of the day after repeated requests from the Chairman, Sw. Vivekananda rose to make a brief, extempore speech beginning with the historic words, "**Sisters and Brothers of America**" (*Abridged Edition of The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda*, 1985, P.1). We are told that when he spoke thus, there arose an applause that lasted

for several minutes. This is due to the fact that he took the audience into his confidence and embraced them all by the yardstick of universal brotherhood. He was not like distinct separate persona pouring out his wisdom on the dais, but a human being speaking to his near and dear ones from the innermost core of his heart. He ensured the rapt attention of listeners and continued his speech with full of serene self-confidence. He ventured the subtleties of his own spiritual intuitions as if he was reading from the pages of an open book. His inherent habit of forfeiting respect to all sects of people coupled with his sense of situation created such an impetus that the audience remained spell bound. Not going into the very detail, he presented before the audience the apparent glory of his religion and the service it had provided to the world. He firmly established the belief which his Guru used to utter that all the paths of worshipping would lead to the same destination viz. to the God. He translated into English a famous hymn to exemplify the same:

As the different streams having their sources in different places all mingle their water in the sea, so, O Lord, the different paths which men take through different tendencies, various though they appear, crooked or straight, all lead to Thee. (*Abridged Edition of The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda*, 1985, P.1)

Notable here is his gift of picking appropriate analogy. He might have chosen other things, to draw parity but quoted only that which was understandable to the audience.

Taking into consideration the aforesaid, we might come to the conclusion that what made Swamiji great were his sense of situation and

choice of language accordingly. He knew very well that the audience was not well aware of the inherent traits and deep philosophy of his religion. So, he only focused on the surface level as far as possible. He entertained a sense of acceptance to proceed further in his visionary goal which was the communion of the East and the West. And all these was made possible due to his strong command over the language (viz. English). Though not a native speaker, his uses of English language was hardly less standard than the rest of the speakers on the platform. His language was very much ornamental and rhythmic. There was not an aura of whimsicality.

Swami Vivekananda as Different from his Contemporaries

The use of language by a person, exclusively from the pedagogical point of consideration is to be evaluated by the contemporary syntactic mode of expression- no matter whether it is in vernacular or in any foreign language, especially English. In the various fields of creativity and language-analysis, we used to search out by-gone days. This is our popular habit. As a result we observed a sharp attitudinal conflict between ancient Indian heritage and western culture impregnated with science. What would be the path- integration or assimilation? There is no denying that before Sw. Vivekananda, the contemporary intelligentsia normally used to tend to the west, even in case of language consideration. Sw. Vivekananda believed that the chief purpose of language is the development of self-conscience. Because conscience specifies change and transition. The chief aim of language is to turn the mirror into windows. Let immaculate wind come, glittering sunshine, violent storms and bi that force our conscience will be recharged. Language according to

Swami Vivekananda should be the voice of our conscience. His is English which is simple, colloquial, extremely communication-rich and absolutely heart-sensitive.

The nineteenth century intellectual climate of Indian society witnessed the advent of modern Western ideas of material progress. Without dogmatically rejecting these ideas, Swami Vivekananda qualified, formulated, distinguished, and contrasted the West from India. He emphasized that the chief cause of India's ruin has been monopolizing the whole education by dint of pride and royal authority, among a handful of men. He appears that if we are to rise again, we shall have to do it by spreading education among the masses and language will be the interlocutor of this adventure. It is true that the metropolitan variety called 'Indian English' lacks that kind of literary vitality in his writings. But it has a different kind of creative vitality that has made Sw. Vivekananda's writings so penetrating and thought-provoking.

Let us have a look on few excerpts made by few eminent Bengali literary figures writing in English:

Thus pressed by the Nazims, the Talukdars, Zeminders pressed the village contractors, and the village contractors preyed upon the ryots. Abwabs after abwabs were imposed. Such of the village contractors as came forward to protest or oppose were incarcerated and ousted, and in the room of hundreds, one, more tractable and willing to submit, was appointed.

The rich are able to protect themselves; the poor require to be protected. The rich instead of needing protection often take

the law into their own hands; the poor far from exercising such a stretch of authority; do not always enjoy even the benefits of the law. The Bengal Ryot belongs to the humble class. He lives by 'sweat of his brow'. (Mitra, Peary Chand: *The Zemindar and the Ryot*. 1846. P.312)

Since my arrival here, I have had much to do in the way of procuring a standing place for myself- no easy matter, I assure you, - especially for a friendless stranger. However, thank God, my trials are, in a certain measure, at an end, and I now begin to look about me very much like a commander of a burque, just having dropped his anchor in a comparatively safe place, after a fearful gale!... (Dutt, Madhu Sudan: *Letter Written to Gourdas*. Madhu Sudan Rachanabali, SahityaSamsad, 1984. P.530)

Viewed with eyes of jealousy the encroachments that were being made in the ancient manners and usages by the influence of western civilization and had steadily forborne to send his son to an English school, which he condemned as a thing not only useless but as positively mischievous. Mathur was early associated with his father in the management of the zemindari and proved an exceedingly apt scholar in the science of chicane. Fraud and torture. (Bankimchandra: *Rajmohan's Wife*, Ch., iv, *BankimRachanabali*, Sahitya Samsad, 1990, p.11)

What do the above-mentioned specimens signify? At least from the syntactic and morphological point of view. Swami

Vivekananda empathized the emotive connotations of linguistic structure which is more appealing for the people in practice. Whereas the other eminent predecessors or contemporaries absolutely led by the British syntax – sometimes rhetorical, sometimes superfluous.

Conclusion

The countries in the south-east Asia (viz. China) and Africa have continuously been working to prepare a simplified version of English language to make them well equipped in the present info-media world. They have succeeded in this sphere and it is beyond any doubt. In India efforts in this regard have been sought forward and are still under process. Our basic need is to build an Indianized English to be as per with the global village. Sw. Vivekananda's language construction is being driven with a purpose- the purpose to communicate, the purpose to reach into the hearts of the masses. So his was an English, which is to be considered as a specimen of '*Indian English*' in the truest sense of the term. Sw. Vivekananda's concept of language construction reminds us that English is no longer the language of the colonial rulers, it is a language of modern India in which words and expressions have recognized rational rather than imported significances and references, alluding to local realities, traditions and ways of feeling.

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